

BUCCAL FILMS: A PROMISING TRANSMUCOSAL SYSTEM FOR ENHANCED DRUG DELIVERY

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ABSTRACT

Buccal films are thin, flexible, and bioadhesive dosage forms designed for transmucosal drug delivery through the buccal mucosa. They offer a promising alternative to conventional oral dosage forms by bypassing hepatic first-pass metabolism and reducing gastrointestinal degradation, thereby improving drug bioavailability. The buccal route is particularly advantageous for the delivery of drugs with poor oral absorption and for biomolecules such as proteins and peptides. Incorporation of bioadhesive polymers enhances residence time and allows controlled or unidirectional drug release toward the mucosa. Buccal films are generally prepared by solvent casting, hot-melt extrusion, or direct milling methods. These films provide rapid onset of action, precise dosing, good patient compliance, and suitability for pediatric and geriatric populations. A wide range of natural and synthetic polymers can be employed to tailor mechanical strength, mucoadhesion, and drug release characteristics. Comprehensive evaluation parameters ensure

quality, safety, and performance of the formulation. Despite limitations such as low dose-loading capacity and mucosal permeability, rational formulation strategies can overcome these challenges. Overall, buccal films represent an efficient, patient-friendly, and cost-effective platform for both local and systemic drug delivery.

KEYWORDS: Buccal films; Transmucosal drug delivery; Controlled drug release.

INTRODUCTION

The pharmaceutical industry has attracted significant attention and has emerged as a key component of the healthcare sector. Continuous advancements in this field have played a vital role in disease treatment, leading to improvements in the quality of life.^[1] Over time, scientists and researchers in the drug development industry have increasingly focused on alternative routes of drug administration to enhance the therapeutic potential of approved products and to overcome the limitations associated with oral delivery. Although the oral route is widely preferred, it presents several challenges, including hepatic first-pass metabolism, gastrointestinal toxicity, and enzymatic degradation within the gastrointestinal tract. To address these issues, systemic drug delivery through alternative routes such as intranasal, buccal/sublingual, pulmonary, and transdermal administration has been successfully explored.^[2] Transmucosal drug delivery routes, involving the mucosal membranes of the nasal, rectal, vaginal, ocular, and oral cavities, provide significant opportunities and advantages over conventional peroral administration for systemic drug delivery. These routes can potentially circumvent hepatic first-pass metabolism, minimize pre systemic drug degradation within the gastrointestinal tract, and, depending on the physicochemical properties of the drug, offer a more favourable enzymatic environment for efficient drug absorption.^[3]

Drug administration sites within the oral cavity include the sublingual region (floor of the mouth), buccal mucosa (inner lining of the cheeks), and gingival tissue.^[4] Advances in biotechnology have led to the availability of hydrophilic, high-molecular-weight therapeutic agents such as proteins and peptides for clinical application. However, oral administration of these biomolecules is limited by enzymatic degradation and poor gastrointestinal absorption. Consequently, the buccal route has gained considerable interest as an effective alternative for the successful systemic delivery of proteins and peptides.^[5]

Figure 1: Mucosal region of mouth.

For systemic transmucosal drug delivery, the buccal mucosa is generally preferred over the sublingual mucosa. This preference is attributed to its relatively lower permeability, which prevents rapid drug absorption and makes it more suitable for formulations designed to achieve sustained or controlled drug release. Additionally, the buccal mucosa is comparatively immobile and easily accessible, rendering it particularly advantageous for the development of retentive drug delivery systems intended for oral transmucosal administration. In recent decades, the use of bioadhesive polymers to extend the residence time of dosage forms has attracted significant interest in transmucosal drug delivery systems. Adhesion is broadly defined as the process by which two surfaces are held together. Bioadhesion refers to the interaction in which two materials, at least one of which is biological in origin, remain attached for a prolonged duration due to interfacial forces. Within pharmaceutical sciences, when such adhesive interactions occur with mucus or mucosal tissues, the process is specifically termed mucoadhesion.^[6]

Characteristics of an Ideal Buccoadhesive System

An ideal buccoadhesive system should exhibit the following characteristics

- It should adhere rapidly to the buccal mucosa and possess adequate mechanical strength.
- It should provide controlled and sustained drug release.
- It should enhance both the rate and extent of drug absorption.
- It should ensure good patient compliance.
- It should not interfere with normal physiological activities such as speaking, eating, or drinking.
- It should enable unidirectional drug release toward the buccal mucosa.
- It should not promote the development of secondary infections, including dental caries.
- It should have a wide margin of safety at both local and systemic levels.
- It should exhibit good resistance to the flushing action of saliva.^[7-9]

Advantages of Buccal Films

- Eliminates the risk of choking.
- Does not require chewing or swallowing.
- Provides a rapid onset of action with reduced side effects.
- Ensure precise dosing compared to liquid dosage forms.
- Effective taste masking can be achieved.
- Offers good mouthfeel and excellent stability.

- Requires a smaller amount of excipients.
- Easy to transport, store, and handle by consumers.
- Cost-effective dosage form.
- Convenient for pediatric and geriatric patients, as well as mentally challenged, disabled, or uncooperative patients.
- Increases the residence time at the site of absorption, thereby enhancing bioavailability.
- Protects the drug from degradation in the gastrointestinal tract and acidic conditions.
- Large surface area of the buccal film enables rapid disintegration and dissolution in the oral cavity.^[10]

Figure 2: Buccal film.

DISADVANTAGES

- Drugs requiring a high dose are difficult to incorporate and administer through buccal films.
- Drugs that are unstable at buccal pH are unsuitable for buccal delivery.
- The presence of antimicrobial agents in the formulation may disturb the normal microbial flora of the buccal cavity.
- The buccal membrane has relatively low permeability, especially when compared with the sublingual membrane.
- Drugs that irritate the oral mucosa, have a bitter taste, cause allergic reactions, or lead to tooth discoloration cannot be effectively formulated as buccal films.
- Swallowing of saliva may result in partial loss of the dissolved or suspended drug, reducing drug availability.^[11]

Figure 3: Mechanism of mucoadhesion.

TYPES OF BUCCAL DRUG DELIVERY DOSAGE FORMS^[12]

1. Buccal bioadhesive tablets
2. Buccal bioadhesive semisolid dosage forms
3. Buccal patches and films
4. Buccal Powders.

1. Buccal bioadhesive tablets

Buccal bioadhesive tablets are solid dosage forms that are slightly moistened before being applied to the buccal mucosa. Single-layer as well as double- and multilayer tablets have been developed using bioadhesive polymers along with suitable excipients.

Marketed products

- Bucastem
- Suscard Buccal P.

2. Buccal bioadhesive semisolid dosage forms

Buccal bioadhesive semisolid dosage forms are prepared by dispersing finely powdered natural or synthetic polymers in polyethylene bases or in aqueous media.

Marketed product

- Orabase

3. Buccal patches and films

Buccal bioadhesive patches are composed of two-layer laminates or multilayer thin films, usually round or oval in shape. They primarily contain a bioadhesive polymeric layer along

with an impermeable backing layer, which ensures unidirectional drug release across the buccal mucosa. Buccal bioadhesive films are generally prepared by dissolving the drug in an alcoholic solution of a bioadhesive polymer.

EXAMPLES

- Isosorbide dinitrate formulated as a unidirectional, erodible buccal film and developed to enhance its bioavailability.
- Buccal films of salbutamol sulphate and terbutaline sulphate designed for the management of asthma.
- Buccoadhesive films containing clindamycin used in the treatment of pyorrhoea.

4. Buccal Powders

Buccal bioadhesive powder dosage forms consist of a blend of the drug with bioadhesive polymers and are applied directly onto the buccal mucosa by spraying. Administration of nifedipine in the form of a buccal tablet and a buccal film has been reported to produce a reduction in diastolic blood pressure.

Manufacturing Methods of Buccal Films^[13]

Buccal films are generally prepared using the following three methods:

1. Solvent casting method
2. Hot-melt extrusion method
3. Direct milling (kneading) method.

1. Solvent Casting Method

Figure 4: Solvent casting method.

Steps involved

- Prepare a casting solution by dissolving the API and polymer in distilled water.
- Remove entrapped air from the solution (deaeration).

- Pour a measured quantity of the solution into a suitable mould.
- Dry the solution under controlled conditions to form a film.
- Cut the dried film into the required size and shape to obtain the final dosage form.^[13]

Figure 5: Steps involved in preparation of Buccal Film.

2. Hot-Melt Extrusion Method

Procedure for preparation of buccal film

Step 1: Polymer pre-treatment

- Polymers are dried in an oven at 50°C for 24 hours to remove moisture.

Step 2: Preparation of ingredients

- All excipients (except the drug) are accurately weighed.
- The materials are passed through a 35-mesh sieve to ensure uniformity.
- Sieved ingredients are mixed thoroughly.

Step 3: Drug blending

- The active drug is added to the excipient mixture.
- Blending is carried out using a twin-shell blender at 25 rpm for 10 minutes to ensure uniform drug distribution.

Step 4: Extrusion process

- The blended material is fed into a hot-melt extruder at a constant rate.
- Extrusion is performed using a co-rotating twin-screw extruder.
- Screw speed, barrel temperature, torque, and die pressure are carefully controlled to form films.

Step 5: Post-extrusion processing

- The extruded films are cut to the required size.

- Films are flushed with nitrogen to prevent oxidation.
- Finally, films are packed in aluminium foil and stored in foil-lined polyethylene bags until further use.^[14]

3. Direct Milling (Kneading) Method

Solvent-free preparation steps

Step 1: Weighing of ingredients

- The API and excipients are accurately weighed.

Step 2: Pre-mixing

- Dry mixing of ingredients is done to achieve initial uniformity.

Step 3: Milling or kneading

- The mixture is processed using a milling or kneading machine without the use of solvents.
- Mechanical force ensures uniform dispersion of the drug.

Step 4: Thickness adjustment

- The mixture is processed to obtain suitable consistency and thickness.

Step 5: Rolling

- The material is passed through rollers lined with a release liner to achieve uniform film thickness.

Step 6: Final processing

- Films are cut or shaped as required.
- Quality checks are performed to ensure uniformity and mechanical strength.

Step 7: Packaging and storage

- Finished films are packed in suitable packaging materials and stored under recommended conditions.^[15]

Applications of Buccal / Oral Films

1. Local treatment of oral diseases

Buccal films are used for localized drug delivery in the treatment of oral conditions such as oral candidiasis, ulcers, and periodontal infections.^[16]

2. Rapid onset of action

Due to fast hydration and direct contact with the buccal mucosa, buccal films provide rapid onset of therapeutic action.^[17]

3. Pediatric and geriatric drug delivery

Buccal films improve patient compliance in pediatric and geriatric populations because they are easy to administer and do not require swallowing.^[18]

4. Controlled drug release

Buccal films can provide controlled and unidirectional drug release, resulting in reduced dosing frequency and improved therapeutic outcomes.^[19]

5. Peptide and protein delivery

Buccal films are suitable for the delivery of peptides and proteins as they protect drugs from enzymatic degradation in the gastrointestinal tract.^[20]

6. Smoking cessation therapy

Buccal films are used in nicotine replacement therapy due to their sustained drug release and improved patient compliance.^[21]

Table 1: Classification of polymer used in buccal films.^[22]

Based on source	
1. Synthetic polymer	Cellulose derivatives, Poly (acrylic acid) polymers, Poly (hydroxyethyl methyl acrylate), Poly (ethylene oxide), Poly (vinyl alcohol), Poly (vinylpyrrolidone), Thiolated polymer, Polyurethanes.
2. Natural polymer	Tragacanth, Sodium alginate, Agarose, Guar gum, Xanthan gum, Karaya gum, carrageenan, Chitosan, Soluble starch, Pectin, Gelatin.
Based on solubility	
1. Water-soluble polymer	Hydroxy Ethyl Cellulose, Hydroxy Propyl Cellulose, PAA, Sodium CMC, HPMC, Sodium alginate, Carbopol
2. Water-insoluble polymer	Chitosan, Ethyl cellulose, Polycarbofil.
Based on charge	
1. Cationic	Chitosan, Dimethylamine ethyl-dextran, Amino dextran .
2. Anionic	Chitosan-EDTA, CMC, CP, pectin, PC, PAA, xanthan gum, sodium CMC, alginate.
3. Non-ionic	Hydroxyethyl starch, PVA, PVP HPC, scleroglucan, poly (ethylene oxide).
Based on generation	

1. First generation	Chitosan, dimethyl amino ethyl-dextran, Amino dextran Chitosan-EDTA, CMC, CP, pectin, PC, PAA, sodium, xanthan gum, sodium CMC alginate, Hydroxy ethyl starch, PVA, PVP HPC, Scleroglucan, Poly (ethylene oxide)
2. Second generation	Lectins, Thiolated polymers

Table 02: summary of published buccal films formulation studies.^[23-31]

SI. No	Author	Method	Polymers	Observation
01	Mahajan HD et al., (2025)	Solvent Casting Method	Hydroxyl propyl methylcellulose E-15,E-5, Polyethylene glycol400, Polyethylene glycol 200,	The mucoadhesive buccal films of azilsartan medoxomil exhibited excellent drug release, strong mucoadhesive properties, and good stability, confirming their suitability for effective buccal drug delivery.
02	MOHAMED MI et al., (2024)	Solvent Casting Method	HPMCHydroxy Propylcellulose (HPC), Sodium Carboxy Methyl Cellulose(Na CMC), Gelatin, Polyvinyl pyrrolidone	Lornoxicam mucoadhesive buccal films were successfully formulated using different polymers and exhibited promising characteristics for efficient drug delivery. The optimized formulation showed good bioadhesive strength, satisfactory drug release, and adequate stability, indicating its potential use in pain management and the treatment of inflammation. Further clinical investigations are required to confirm the therapeutic efficacy and practical applicability of these films.
03	MADHURI P et al., (2024)	Solvent Casting Method	HPMCK4M, HPMC K15M, HPMC K100M, Ethyl cellulose, Sodium CMC and HPC.	The optimized mucoadhesive buccal films of abacavir sulphate exhibited a significant improvement in oral bioavailability compared with marketed formulations. In vivo pharmacokinetic studies in rabbits showed prolonged mucoadhesion in the buccal cavity. This extended residence time likely contributed to the

				enhanced bioavailability of the drug.
04	Vajrala LL et al.,(2023)	Solvent Casting Method	HPMC, PVP	The study successfully established basil seed mucilage as a cost-effective and suitable natural polymer for the formulation of buccal films. The optimized formulation exhibited excellent drug content uniformity and strong mucoadhesive properties, supporting its potential for further development. The carvedilol buccal films demonstrated promising physicochemical characteristics, indicating their suitability as an effective controlled drug delivery system.
05	Mady OY et al.,(2023)	Solvent Casting Method	HPMC E3, HPMC K4 and C 940	The study showed that doxycycline hyclate-loaded mucoadhesive buccal films are effective in providing prolonged antibiotic release and exhibit favorable in vitro and in vivo performance. The formulation produced encouraging results in the treatment of periodontitis in rats, with improvements in clinical parameters and a reduction in MMP-8 levels. Further clinical studies in humans are required to confirm the potential of these films for localized oral therapy.
06	Korelc K et al., (2023)	Solvent Casting Method	Chitosan types Chitopharm™, CM, M and L, Viscosan	The study successfully formulated child-friendly mucoadhesive films and wafers for controlled drug delivery using chitosan-based systems. The optimized formulations exhibited favorable mucoadhesive properties, appropriate drug release profiles, and good

				biocompatibility. In particular, the mucoadhesive wafers demonstrated more sustained drug release, indicating their potential as a promising alternative to films for pediatric applications.
07	Abdella S et al.,(2022)	Solvent Casting Method	HPMC, Kollicoat IR (PVA-PEGcopolymer)	The mucoadhesive buccal films of estradiol prepared using co-solvency and nano-emulsion techniques exhibited excellent drug release, permeability, and mechanical properties. The nano-emulsion method produced particularly promising results, with enhanced drug permeation and the potential for sustained estradiol release. These films may represent a viable approach for improving hormonal therapy, especially in the management of menopausal symptoms.
08	Kristó K et al., (2022)	Solvent Casting Method	Chitosan 80/1000	Ascorbic acid-loaded chitosan films were successfully developed as buccal drug delivery systems, demonstrating the role of ascorbic acid as a plasticizer and its influence on film properties. The optimal ascorbic acid concentration was identified as 2%, providing favorable drug release characteristics for cationic drugs. These findings offer valuable insights into the structural design and formulation of chitosan-based films for future drug delivery applications.
09	Pamlényi K et al., (2022)	Solvent Casting Method	HPMC, Sodium alginate	The study successfully developed buccal films using sodium alginate (SA), which exhibited strong mechanical

				strength and good mucoadhesive properties. Interactions among excipients, particularly hydrogen bonding, contributed to improved thermal and mechanical stability of the films. Several promising formulations were identified, indicating their potential suitability for buccal drug delivery applications
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Table 3: Recently Reported Research Work on Buccal Films.

SL NO	Product Name	Active Ingredient (API)	Manufacturer / Marketed By	Use / Category
1.	Zolmitriptan Rapidfilm	Zolmitriptan	Labtec (Germany)	Migraine relief
2.	Setofilm®	Ondansetron	BioAlliance Pharma (Europe)	Antiemetic
3.	Donepezil Rapidfilm®	Donepezil	Labtec (Europe & US)	Alzheimer's
4.	Suboxone® Film	Buprenorphine	Monosol Rx	Opioid dependence
5.	Klonopin Wafers	Clonazepam	Solvay Pharmaceuticals	Antianxiety

EVALUATION

1. Thickness Measurement

The thickness of the films is measured using an electronic digital micrometer, digital vernier caliper, or microscrew gauge.^[32] Measurements are taken at various positions of the film, including the corners and the center, and the average thickness is calculated to ensure uniformity.

2. *In Vitro* Dissolution Studies

In vitro drug release studies are carried out using a USP dissolution apparatus. The temperature is maintained at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$, with the paddle rotation speed set at 50 rpm, and 900 mL of dissolution medium is used. Samples are withdrawn at predetermined time intervals and replaced with an equal volume of fresh medium. The percentage drug release is determined by analyzing the samples using a UV spectrophotometer at the specified wavelength.^[33]

3. Chemical Stability Studies

Chemical compatibility studies are carried out to detect any possible interactions among the formulation components. Techniques such as Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy, Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC), and X-ray Diffraction (XRD) are commonly employed to evaluate compatibility and stability of the ingredients.

4. Surface Morphology

Surface morphology of the films is examined using various microscopic techniques such as scanning electron microscopy (SEM), electron microscopy, and scanning tunneling microscopy. Among these, SEM is most commonly used to evaluate the surface characteristics, including shape, size, and number of pores present on the film surface.^[34]

5. Swelling Study

The swelling behavior of the film is determined by placing the sample on an agar plate and incubating it at $37 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$. The increase in film diameter and weight is recorded at different time intervals ranging from 1 to 5 hours. Swellability is calculated using the following equation^[35]

- $\% \text{ Swelling} = [(X_t - X_o) / X_o] \times 100$

where X_o represents the initial weight or diameter of the film and X_t represents the weight or diameter at time t .

6. Surface pH

Measurement of surface pH is essential to evaluate the potential for mucosal irritation. Films with highly acidic or basic pH may cause irritation to the mucosa. The film is initially placed in 1.0 mL of distilled water adjusted to $\text{pH } 6.5 \pm 0.05$ for 2 hours using a specially designed glass tube. The surface pH is then measured by placing a combined glass electrode in contact with the film surface for 1 minute.^[36]

7. Folding Endurance

Folding endurance is an indicator of the flexibility and mechanical strength of the buccal film. It is determined by repeatedly folding a selected film sample at an angle of 180° until it breaks. Alternatively, the film may be folded up to 300 times without breaking. Folding endurance is expressed as the number of folds the film withstands before rupture.^[37]

8. Moisture Content

The percentage moisture content of the films is calculated by measuring the difference between the initial weight of the film and the weight after storage in a desiccator for a specified period. Calcium chloride is placed in the desiccator, and the setup is maintained for 24 hours. The percentage moisture content is calculated using the following equation^[38]

- % Moisture content = $[(\text{Initial weight} - \text{Final weight}) / \text{Final weight}] \times 100$.

9. Moisture Uptake

For moisture uptake studies, the film sample is initially weighed and kept in a desiccator at room temperature. After 24 hours, the film is exposed to 84% relative humidity using a saturated potassium chloride solution until a constant weight is achieved. The percentage moisture uptake is calculated using the following formula.^[39]

- % Moisture uptake = $[(\text{Final weight} - \text{Initial weight}) / \text{Initial weight}] \times 100$

CONCLUSION

Buccal films are an efficient and patient-friendly transmucosal drug delivery system that overcome key limitations of conventional oral dosage forms. They bypass hepatic first-pass metabolism and reduce gastrointestinal degradation, thereby improving drug bioavailability and therapeutic efficacy. The use of bioadhesive polymers enhances residence time on the buccal mucosa and enables controlled or unidirectional drug release. Various manufacturing methods such as solvent casting, hot-melt extrusion, and direct milling allow the development of films with desirable mechanical strength and flexibility. A wide range of natural and synthetic polymers provides formulation versatility for different drugs and clinical needs. Recent studies have demonstrated successful application of buccal films for analgesics, antihypertensives, antimicrobials, hormones, and CNS drugs. Comprehensive evaluation parameters ensure quality, safety, and performance of the dosage form. Although challenges such as limited dose loading and low permeability exist, they can be minimized through rational formulation design. Overall, buccal films represent a promising, convenient, and cost-effective platform for both local and systemic drug delivery.

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